

3-D DYNAMIC SIMULATION OF FLEXIBLE FIBRE WITH ARTICULATED BODY SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A new discrete element method is developed to study the dynamic motion of a fibre. The fibre model is represented by an articulated body system. This paper presents the 3-D dynamic modelling of a suspended fibre using recursive algorithms based on the Newton-Euler equations of the articulated body system. The relative acceleration at each connection, which named joint, between two bodies is given as a function of the joint positions, velocities and accelerations. This method guarantees a facility of implementation, fast resolutions and high numerical stability and has a good convergence rate.

Results of several dynamic simulations of long fibres subjected to falling and bending tests with one fixed or constrained end are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

In aeronautics, there is a growing interest for structural composite materials manufacturing with automated processes. The process of automated dry fibre placement allows lying down fibre tow thanks to the deposition head (which includes a heating source and a compaction roller). The fibrous preform is subsequently impregnated by a loco viscosity polymer to preform a composite after polymerization. The quality of the final part depends partially on the accuracy of the dry fibre tape positioning during placement and the adhesion efficiency.

The advantages and drawbacks of the automated dry tows placement process compared to the automated prepreg tape placement and the manual woven, unidirectional and multi-axial fabrics placement process are presented in Table 1.

Several numerical models have been developed to study the mechanical behaviour of tows at the fibre-scale, taking into account the behaviour of each fibre and fibre-fibre contact [3]. For instance, models addressed the motion of a single fibre viewed as a motion of a Cosserat rod [7], a series of beads [14, 15], rods [11] and spheroids/needles [8, 9, 10]. Some models have been developed based on finite element method by Durville [2, 3] and digital element method by Wang and Sun [12] and Wang et al [13].

Advantages	Drawbacks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dry tow is much easier to bend or sheared • Control of dry tows orientation • Metering of fibres guaranteed (until 60%) • Preform can be kept unlimited shelf life • Dry tow and resin purchased individually are cheaper than the prepreg tow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spring back of preform • Problem of mismatch between designed and real tow path because of overlap and gap • The deposition head bulks large • The problem of the adhesion of the first layer

Table 1: The advantages and drawbacks of the automated dry tows placement

The articulated body model using a reduced coordinate formulation and Newton-Euler equations developed by Featherstone [4] and generalized by Khalil [5] is used to develop a 3-D dynamics model for a long flexible fibre. The fibre motion is simulated by solving the forward dynamics of the multi-body system using the recursive Articulated-Body Algorithm, and successively integrating the accelerations.

2 FIBER MODEL

2.1 Geometric Modelling

The fiber is treated as a serial rigid-body system composed of a sequence of $n + 1$ bodies of equal length l and n spherical joints. Each spherical joint is represented by an equivalent combination of three rotational [6] joints what gives a system with $3n$ rotational joints and $(3n+1)$ bodies (see Figure: 1). The bodies $(3j-1)$ and $(3j-2)$, for $(j = 1, \dots, n)$, are virtual zero length and zero mass; thus, there are no forces acting on them.

2.1 Dynamic Modelling

The direct dynamic model gives the joint accelerations in terms of the joint positions, velocities and torques. It is represented in [5] by:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \mathbf{\Gamma}, \mathbf{f}_e, \mathbf{G}) \quad (1)$$

with

- $\mathbf{\Gamma}$: is the vectors of joint torques, depending on whether the joint is rotational or linear respectively;
- \mathbf{G} : is the gravity acceleration;
- \mathbf{q} : is the vector of joint positions;
- $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$: is the vector of joint velocities;
- $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}$: is the vector of joint accelerations;
- \mathbf{f}_e : is the vector of forces and moments due to the contact between the environment and the articulated-body;

The model is based on the recursive Newton–Euler equations and consists of three recursive calculations:

- First Forward Step ($j = 1, \dots, n$): we calculate the screw transformation matrices, velocities and the components of accelerations of and external couple for each body of the system
- Backward Step ($j = n, \dots, 1$): we compute the spatial inertia matrices and external couple of each body with taking into account of the influence of the other bodies which allows to express $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}$

- Second Forward ($j = 1, \dots, n$): we calculate $\ddot{\mathbf{q}}_j$ and ${}^j\mathbb{V}_j$ for each body. This step is initialized by ${}^0\mathbb{V}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{G} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 1} \end{bmatrix}$, with \mathbf{G} is the acceleration of gravity in order to take the effect of gravity forces on all bodies of the system.

The joints ($3j$) can correspond to twisting or tension/compression behavior and the joints ($3j - 1$) and ($3j - 2$) can correspond to bending or shearing behavior.

In this work the motions of an inextensible fiber is modelled by an articulated body system in the case of the joints ($3j$) correspond to twisting behavior and the joints ($3j - 1$) and ($3j - 2$) correspond to bending behavior.

The joint elasticity is modeled as a linear torsional spring for cylindrical joints, which produce a torque proportional to the misalignment of two consecutive elements. Let $\Delta\mathbf{q}$ be the $(3n \times 1)$ vector of the joint deformations and $\mathbf{diag}(\mathbf{K})$ is the $(3n \times 3n)$ diagonal matrix whose elements are the stiffness coefficients at each joint, where $k_j = \frac{I_{sec}E}{l}$ is the stiffness of the joint with E the Young's modulus of the fiber, and I_{sec} is the momentum of inertia of the section. The total torque in the *body_j* is the sum of the torque from the parent, *body_{j-1}*, and the children, *body_{j+1}*:

$$\mathbf{r} = -\mathbf{diag}(\mathbf{K}) \cdot \Delta\mathbf{q} = - \begin{bmatrix} k_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & & & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & k_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ q_{3j-2} - q_{3(j+1)-2} \\ q_{3j-1} - q_{3(j+1)-1} \\ q_{3j} - q_{3(j+1)} \\ \vdots \\ q_{3n-2} \\ q_{3n-1} \\ q_{3n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

To improve the model we can add a viscous damping at each joint:

$$\mathbf{D} = -\mathbf{diag}(\mathbf{C}) \cdot \Delta\dot{\mathbf{q}} = - \begin{bmatrix} c_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & & \ddots & \\ & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & & & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & c_n \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vdots \\ \dot{q}_{3j-2} - \dot{q}_{3(j+1)-2} \\ \dot{q}_{3j-1} - \dot{q}_{3(j+1)-1} \\ \dot{q}_{3j} - \dot{q}_{3(j+1)} \\ \vdots \\ \dot{q}_{3n-2} \\ \dot{q}_{3n-1} \\ \dot{q}_{3n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where: $\Delta\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ is the $(3n \times 1)$ vector of the joint velocities and $\mathbf{diag}(\mathbf{C})$ is the $(3n \times 3n)$ diagonal matrix whose elements are the damping coefficients at each joint.

By companying bending stiffness and viscous damping we obtain a viscoelastic Kelvin-Voigt model.

3 NUMERICAL TESTS

Using the recursive Newton-Euler Algorithms we obtain the mathematical model of fiber in a concise form:

$$\ddot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}, \ddot{\mathbf{q}}) \quad (4)$$

The equivalent first-order differential system of system (4) with initial conditions can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{Y} = F(t, Y, \dot{Y}) & Y(t_0) = Y_0 \text{ with:} \\ Y = \begin{bmatrix} q \\ \dot{q} \end{bmatrix} & \text{and } \dot{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q} \\ \ddot{q} \end{bmatrix} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The system obtained is classified as an Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs). However, it is different from a standard system of ODEs because the function F depends on Y and \dot{Y} , which means there are several derivatives in each ODE. The system can be classified as implicit ODEs or in generally as a system of Differential Algebraic Equations (DAEs) written in the fully implicit form:

$$G(t, Y, \dot{Y}) = \dot{Y} - F(t, Y, \dot{Y}) = \mathbf{0} \quad (6)$$

To solve the obtained system (6) over time, the existing algorithm in MATLAB named “ode15i” has been used. It is based on the Backward Differentiation Formulas (BDF) of order five with an error estimator.

3.1 Freely falling test

In this numerical test, a 2-D dynamic of a freely falling articulated-body system, which represent a long and flexible yarn, with one free extremity and one constrained (fixed) extremity is addressed. The initial conditions of this test are: the generalized velocities are assumed equal to zero $\dot{q}_j(t = 0) = 0$ for $(j = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ and as the initial configuration of the system we use a catenary curve with the position of the tip is $(x = 0.2 \text{ m}, y = -0.5 \text{ m}, z = 0 \text{ m})$. The used parameters are: $n = 30$ (number of bodies), $nl = 1 \text{ m}$ (total length) and $nm = 0.5 \text{ kg}$ (total mass). This input data are the ones adopted in [5], from which our results will be compared.

Figure 1: Comparison between configurations of a falling rope obtained (a) in the work of Fritzkowski and Kaminski [5] and (b) with the proposed model with $n = 30$

Comparing the configurations of the Figure.1, some differences are noted at $t = 1.5 s$, $t = 2.0 s$ and $t = 2.5 s$. Those at $t = 0.0 s$ and $t = 1.0 s$ are very similar. The reason of these differences is due to the fact that the system solved is a system of Differential Algebraic Equations and Fritzkowski and Kaminski [5] used the MEBDFV. However, all simulations used the “Ode15i” solver available in MATLAB which is based on BDF method which less efficient than MEBDFV.

A simulation has been run with the same parameters except $n = 80$ and compared to configurations obtained with $n = 70$. No significant difference has been noticed. Obviously, the results obtained with identical parameters but several numbers of elements n are more compatible for a higher n .

Concentrate on the evolution of the total energy of the model over time. Initially, due to the initially conditions the system has zero kinetic energy and a given, non-zero, potential energy. According to Figure.2 (a) and during the falling of the yarn, the kinetic energy increases while the potential energy decreases. Despite the use of optimum options (JPatern, Initial Conditions...) available in “Ode15i” solver, the computed total energy of the system shows some sharp peaks. The first peak arises when the yarn becomes approximately straight and the other ones appear when the system becomes chaotic because of the full rotations of elements around the joints which are rapid and unnatural.

Making the system more dissipative, the motion of the articulated-body system does not become as chaotic despite its rapid fall. Referring to the figure.2 (b), the dissipative forces which are proportional to velocities eliminate almost all the sharp peaks and makes the system non conservative.

Figure 2: Energy Balance for a system (a) without any elasticity or damping (b) with damping
 $F_v = 10^{-3} \text{ N.m.s}$

3.2 Test of yarn at full extension and attached to moving support

The case of 3-D dynamic of an articulated-body system is studied for a yarn at full extension along z_axis with one free extremity and the other one is attached to a moving support with the following rheonomic constraints:

$$\mathbf{P} = \begin{bmatrix} R(t).A.\sin(\pi.B.t) \\ R(t).A.\sin(\pi.B.t + \frac{\pi}{2}) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

with:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} R(t) = 0 & (t = 0) \\ R(t) = B \cdot t - \frac{\sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot B \cdot t)}{2 \cdot \pi} & (\frac{1}{B} \geq t > 0) \\ R(t) = 1 & (\frac{1.5}{B} \geq t > \frac{1}{B}) \\ R(t) = 1 - B \cdot (t - \frac{1.5}{B}) - \frac{\sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot B \cdot (t - \frac{1.5}{B}))}{2 \cdot \pi} & (\frac{2.5}{B} \geq t > \frac{1.5}{B}) \\ R(t) = 0 & (t > \frac{2.5}{B}) \end{array} \right.$$

where A and B are constants, here: $A = 0.025 [m]$ and $B = 5[s^{-1}]$ and $R(t)$ is the ramp function.

At the beginning of simulation, the system is at full extension along z_axis and during the simulation the gravity is applying along z_axis . Combining the spiral motion of the support due to the rheonomic constraints presented in Figure.3, and the gravity, leads to crating mechanical wave which starts traveling along rope from the constrained extremity to the free one.

In the interest of explaining the mechanical wave propagation along the rope, the total energy changes of several elements have represented in Figure.4. A greatest peak occurs at the five last elements which signify the first inverse of the wave propagation and it noticed that the next ones were less noticeable. Due to the wave inversion a specific series of peaks starts and remains until the end of the simulation.

Figure 3: (a) Constrain functions and (b) Support trajectory

Figure 4: Total energy of several elements to illustrate the spiral wave propagation

2 CONCLUSION

In this paper we have focused on the 3-D dynamic fiber model to study 2-D and 3-D yarn motions with two types of constraints, scleronomic and rheonomic. The yarn is modelled as a chain of rigid cylinders and its dynamics is simulated using recursive algorithms which based on the Newton-Euler equations. This approach leads to the lowest computational complexity $O(N)$ and produces a system of Differential Algebraic Equations (DAEs) written in the fully implicit form, which need to be solved numerically.

Indisputably, the considered method to simulate the 3-D dynamic of fiber exhibits powerful capabilities to study the dynamic of different scales of fibers ($\mu m \geq diameters \geq m$) separately or together taking account of the fiber-fiber contacts. The promising results make it merit studying a mechanical behavior of fibrous media, with the good contact laws and numerical methods.

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